

Probability Distributions, Information and Distributed Quantity

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In many cases, probability distributions are obtained by considering the number of ways one may place particles in various cells. This leads to expressions involving combinatorics with Stirling's high number approximation being used together with the idea of permutations of identical particles only counting once. Examples include a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas and a three dimensional spherical random walk problem (1). In general, the \ln of the number of arrangements (or probability of the arrangements) is maximized subject to a constraint. This constraint, however, is "special" in that it represents the distributed variable in the problem such that this variable is additive.

In this note, we try to obtain the same results without combinatorics and Stirling's approximation by considering the quantity which is distributed (for example energy or spatial volume) and the idea of a lack of information. We suggest that one should be able to directly consider the distributed variable because the constraint in the entropy maximization problem is not a general mathematical constraint, but the distributed variable. Thus the maximization approach is a little unusual. For example, in an MB gas, the constraint is $\sum_i e_i n(e_i)$, but mathematically $\sum_i e_i^k n(e_i)$ could be used or any other e_i function, but the exponent of the probability is governed by the constraint function. This suggests a more direct approach to obtaining the probability which we consider here.

Maxwell-Boltzmann Gas and Combinatorics

It is possible to find the probability distribution $n(e_i)$ where e_i is an energy and $n(e_i)$ is the probability for a particle to have e_i subject to $E = \sum_i n(e_i) e_i$ ((1)). We note immediately that the constraint, although reasonable, does not seem unique. In fact, $\sum_i f(e_i) n(e_i)$ where f is any function should also be an allowable constraint, but it is not. In fact, the constraint function has to be the distributed variable which is the variable which is stochastically changed and is additive, it seems. In the case of an MB gas, the condition of elastic scattering implies energy is the distributed variable. Momentum is conserved and linked to the particle scattering in various directions, but given elastic collisions, it is energy which is distributed.

An approach using combinatorics is to consider N total particles where N is very large and consider the different number of ways to choose different groupings $n(e_i)$. One then maximizes the number of groupings subject to the constraint ((1)). Thus the main idea is to think in terms of maximization as yielding the average $n(e_i)$ values.

$$\text{Number of arrangements} = \frac{N!}{\prod_i [N n(e_i)]!} \quad \text{Subject to } \sum_i n(e_i) e_i = E \quad ((2))$$

$\ln(\text{number of arrangements}) = C_1 - \sum_i N n(e_i) \ln(e_i)$ using Stirling's approximation.

Maximization $\ln(\text{number of arrangements})$ subject to ((1)) yields:

$n(e_i) = C_2 \exp(-e_i/T)$ where C_2 and T are constants such that $\sum_i n(e_i) = 1$ and ((1))

The factorial approach already accounts for the notion of identical particles and counts permutations only once.

Maxwell-Boltzmann Gas, Information and Distribution

In keeping with the notion of information, we argue one does not require the notion of arrangements or maximization. One need only ask: What is the distributed quantity and what information is associated with it. The first question is already answered in the above section because one seeks $n(e_i)$. Thus energy is the distributed quantity. It is directly affected by the stochastic process in the problem, namely particle scattering, and is additive.

The notion of information in equilibrium is that a certain amount of energy is associated with a certain probability. Thus it does not matter if one particle contains all the energy or ten particles have energies which add to this same amount. The product probabilities of the latter should equal the probability of the former. Thus:

$$e_3 = e_1 + e_2 \quad \text{and} \quad n(e_3) = n(e_1)n(e_2) \quad ((3))$$

Taking the \ln of the latter and linking with the former yields: $n(e_i) = C_2 \exp(-e_i/T)$ which is the same as the factorial result. The calculator, however, is simpler and focuses more on information we argue.

Maxwell-Boltzmann and Phase Space Factor

There are two further considerations linked to the Maxwell-Boltzmann gas. First, if $e_i = \pi \cdot \pi / 2m$ there is a phase space factor of $\pi \cdot \pi \cdot d\pi$ associated with $\exp(-e_i/T) = \exp(-\pi \cdot \pi / (2mT))$. Thus the distribution approach gives a raw probability which may be enhanced by phase space considerations.

The second consideration relates to volume. Energy was chosen as the distributed variable because it is the variable associated with the stochastic process i.e. elastic scattering and is additive. Boxes of volume are also additive, but not governed directly by the stochastic process (i.e. collisions). Rather a collision occurs at a given point and distributes energy. The different directions in which the particle moves are consequences of conservation of momentum, but the condition of elastic scattering is also imposed and this governs the distribution of energy. Thus in an MB gas, a particle has an equal probability to be at any point in space if there is no potential. Even if there is a potential, it is not associated with a stochastic process and so the spatial density does not follow from the distributed variable arguments given above, but rather from a pressure-force balance.

Spherical 3D Random Walk with Combinatorics and Stirling's Approximation

Following (1), one may formulate the 3D spherical walk using factorials and maximizing probability subject to a constraint. The idea is that given spherical symmetry one seeks p_k , the

probability for a particle to be in the k th shell which is at radius r_k . The probability associated with the k th shell itself is proportional to $4\pi r_k^2$ or r_k^2 . In (1) this is called q_k . If there are N particles where N is very large, then the probability for a certain arrangement with N_k particles in each shell is (as given in (1)):

$$\text{probability}(\text{arrangements}) = \frac{N! \prod_k q_k^{N_k}}{(N_k)!} \quad ((4))$$

The $(N_k)!$ denominator seems to account for different permutations of particles being counted once. The idea is then to take “ln” of ((4)) and use Stirling’s approximation. This yields (as in (1)):

$$\ln(\text{Probability}) = C_1 - \sum_k N_k \ln(N_k/q_k) \quad ((5))$$

In (1) a constraint is then imposed namely: $\sum_k r_k^2 N_k = R^2$ ((6)) where r_k^2 is like a radius squared and ((5)) maximized subject to this constraint. One may note that the constraint chosen will essentially yield the exponential behaviour of the distribution. (One might ask why $\sum_k N_k$ could not have been used as a constraint? Etc if this is a mathematical procedure. Rather we argue that a “special” constraint must be used, namely one using the distributed variable. Thus this is not really a maximization of entropy subject to a constraint in the system.)

Maximizing ((5)) with respect to ((6)) yields:

$$N_k = C r_k^2 \exp(-C_3 r_k^2) \quad ((7))$$

In other words one obtains a Gaussian multiplied by r^2 . The r^2 terms may be thought of as a phase factor like $\pi \cdot \pi \cdot dp$ in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, we argue. One may ask: Why did the $\pi \cdot \pi \cdot dp$ term have to be manually added in the MB case, while r^2 appears automatically in the above. The MB case deals with energy as the distributed variable and this is a scalar. The statistical considerations apply to the distributed variable, but a given distributed variable, say energy, may be associated with a second variable, say the momentum vector, which enhances the probability because one e value may map into many momentum cells. In particular, if one uses a spherical picture, a single e points to a single $p^2/2m$ value, but any cell in a shell with radius p satisfies this criterion. There are more cells in a large p shell than in a small p one.

For the 3D spherical random walk problem, the distributed variable is volume proportional to r^3 for a shell as one deals with shells. Thus there is not a second mapping. Furthermore, the r^2 factor has been added as an extra piece of information i.e. as q_k .

In the next section, one may see that using volume as a distribution variable may yield a B_k i.e. p_k without the r^2 factor which needs to be added manually (because it is not added as a q_k .)

Spherical 3D Random Walk with Information and Distribution

In this section, we ask: What is the variable being distributed? We argue that it is the volume of a shell because the stochastic process of a random walk directly chooses a shell in space. Thus one may consider a distribution of B_k probabilities linked with various spherical shells. The

probability to pull out a shell with volume 3 is the same as the product probability:
 $B(\text{shell1})B(\text{shell2})$ if $V_1+V_2=V_3$.

Thus particles are stochastically assigned to shells. In such a case:

$$V_1+V_2=V_3 \quad ((8a)) \quad \text{and} \quad B_3 = B_2*B_1 \quad ((8b)) \quad \text{and} \quad V \text{ is proportional to } rr$$

Taking \ln of ((8b)) and linking with ((8a)) (just as in the energy distribution case) one has:

$$B_i = C \exp(-C_3 rr) \quad ((9))$$

Each r , however, is associated with a variety of (x,y,z) values lying in the r shell. In fact there are $4\pi r^2 dr$ such cells, so the full probability is:

$$P(r,t) = C rr \exp(-C_3(t) rr) \quad ((10))$$

One may note that this is a time-dependent problem because the random walk means that the system spreads out in time.

One may also note that in ((4)) an extra piece of information, namely q_k proportional to r^k , is used and so one does not need to add the factor rr at the end. In ((8b)), this piece of information is missing. One only considers the probability to pick a shell, ignoring the cells within it.

We note that in the distributed variable approach, it is the distributed variable, i.e. energy in the case of an MB gas or shell volume in the case of 3D random walk, which is the variable appearing in the constraint. Thus this bypasses the somewhat arbitrariness of choosing a constraint in the maximization of $\ln(\text{arrangements})$ approach. In fact, the constraint must use the distributed variable which seems to make the extremization problem a little artificial as the exponential property of the probability is governed directly by the function in the constraint.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that a factorial/Stirling's law approach is often taken to formulate a probability based on a distribution scheme. The logarithm of this quantity is then maximized subject to a constraint to yield the correct probability distribution. In particular, this approach is applied to a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas and spherical 3D random walk in the literature. We caution that sometimes it is difficult to choose the constraint used in the sense that there could be different constraints. Usually the simplest is chosen. For example, instead of choosing $\sum_i e_i n(e_i) = E$ why couldn't one choose: $\sum_i e_i^2 n(e_i) = Q$ where Q is some constant? In fact, the constraint governs the exponential behaviour of the distribution and it seems that it is not in fact arbitrary, but linked to the distribution variable. This suggests that the maximization approach is a little contrived (in the sense of the choice of the constraint.)

In this note, we consider the idea of focusing on a distribution variable which is changed stochastically in a problem (e.g. energy in an elastic collision) and is additive.. In equilibrium, we argue there is no information to favour a single energy e_3 or two energies $e_1+e_2=e_3$ etc for the

Maxwell-Boltzmann gas. For the spherical 3D random walk we argue that shell volume is the distributed variable as it is directly involved in the stochastic process i.e. each random walk step may move into the next shell, or the previous or the same etc. Thus particles are distributed to various shells such that if $V_3=V_1+V_2$, then $B_3 = B_1*B_2$ where B_1 is the probability to pick shell 1. Taking \ln and linking to the sum of volumes leads to $B_i = C \exp(-C^3 r_i \cdot r_i)$. The number of cells within a shell is proportional to $r_i \cdot r_i \cdot d|r_i|$ so one has an overall probability of $C r_i \exp(-C^3 r_i \cdot r_i)$.

References

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